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D2.1 List of Widening Beneficiaries and Projects

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7. Update of unique organisations introduced to the WiderAdvance Facility
8. Appendix: Update of list of organisations and projects
9. Appendix: Addition of the distribution table

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1. Introduction & data protection - privacy statement

The present deliverable concerns the first bundle of beneficiaries and projects that accepted to receive information about the widerAdvance Facility from the project's partners. This list is the result of the initial mapping exercise under Task 2.1 which mapped all Widening organisations taking part either as Coordinators and/or as participants across the projects they appeared to be participating following official public EU sources, notably the EU Dashboard and secondarily, CORDIS. The Widening actions mapped were funded under Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe.

Task 2.1 is a continuous one and mapping will be updated as new beneficiaries arise from recurrent Widening calls as well as from new calls in the WP2025 and WP2026-2027. In the course of the project's duration, more beneficiaries will be contacted in order to be informed about the widerAdvance Facility. Nevertheless, new beneficiaries and projects coming up from calls of the WP 2025, such as the Widening Pre-Accelerator and the European Excellence Hubs, just to name a few, will be able to apply at more advanced cut-offs due to the time needed to generate an applicable results for the widerAdvance Facility.

Data protection and privacy

This deliverable reports only institutional and project-level information obtained from publicly accessible EU sources (including CORDIS and the EU Dashboard) and/or information provided by organisations in their official capacity. It does not include personal data within the meaning of Article 4(1) GDPR. No processing of personal data has been performed for the purposes of this deliverable, and no profiling or automated decision-making (Article 22 GDPR) is involved.

2. Executive summary

RUIZIA, as a major task contributor and FORTH as WP Leader, worked mainly through the Dashboard through the “Self-service BI” which allows customization. In case were it was needed to verify project eligibility, information was retrieved from EU CORDIS.

Following consultation at consortium level, beneficiary organisations involved in projects stemming from the below calls were extracted from the Dashboard:

- Teaming for Excellence (stage 2)
- Twinning (bottom-up, Green Deal, Western Balkans, H2020)
- ERA Chairs (H2020+Horizon Europe)
- Widening/ERA Fellowships (H2020 - Horizon Europe)
- Excellence Hubs
- European Excellence Initiative
- ERA Talents
- Hop-on
- Pathways to Synergies

The beneficiaries of the above-mentioned calls were split per unique beneficiary per country with complete project details, in order to be handed to the project partners to begin selecting the most promising candidates to disseminate information about the widerAdvance Facility. Therefore, 38 unique organizations representing 100 projects (94 unique) were provided individual sessions about the WiderAdvance Facility.

In the near future, new beneficiary organisations may benefit from the widerAdvance Facility’s services, resulting from the calls of WP2025 such as the European Excellence Initiative, EIC Pre-Accelerator, Hop-on facility, Support to R&I Policy making in EU enlargement countries, Implemented co-funded action plans for connected regional innovation valleys in Widening Countries.

3. Mapping of relevant Widening calls

Following internal discussions from the start of the project, the beneficiaries and projects of the following calls were mapped:

Widening projects	Topic IDs	Horizon 2020	Topic IDs	Horizon Europe WP 2021-2022	Horizon Europe WP 2023-2025	Total
Teaming for Excellence (Phase 2 in Horizon 2020), Teaming for Excellence (Stage-2 in Horizon Europe)	WIDESPREAD-01-2016-2017, WIDESPREAD-01-2018-2019	25	WIDERA-2022-ACCESS-01-01-TwoStage, WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-01-01-TwoStage	14	11	25

Twining	H2020-TWINN-2015, WIDESPREAD-05-2017, WIDESPREAD-03-2018, WIDESPREAD-05-2020	211	WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03-01, WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-01, WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-02-02,	106	113	219
Twining for Western Balkans			WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-02-01	17		17
ERA Chairs	WIDESPREAD-02-2014, WIDESPREAD-03-2017, WIDESPREAD-04-2019, WIDESPREAD-06-2020	59	WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-01-01, WIDERA-2023-TALENTS-01-01	34	38	72
Excellence Hubs	N/A	N/A	WIDERA-2022-ACCESS-04-01, WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-07-01	13	11	24
European Excellence Initiative			WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-05-01, WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-03-01	9	12	21
Widening/ ERA Fellowship (H2020/ HE)			WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-02-01, WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-04-01, WIDERA-2023-TALENTS-02-01, WIDERA-2024-TALENTS-02-01 (pending evaluation results), WIDERA-2025-TALENTS-01-01 (to be launched)	130	54	184
ERA Talents			WIDERA-2022-TALENTS-03-01, WIDERA-2024-	9	13	22

			TALENTS-03-01			
Hop On Facility			WIDERA-2022-ACCESS-07-01, WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-06-01	31	73	104
Pathways to Synergies			WIDERA-2023-ACCESS-04-01	16		16
Sub Total of projects		295		379	325	704
Unique beneficiaries	927					

The table above resulted to more than 900 unique organisations. These organisations are, by average, beneficiaries to multiple projects, either as participant or coordinator, and a subset of these organisations will positively self-assess of having generated **Key Exploitable Results**.

4. How we worked

The partners consulted the individual excel sheet with project details per widening beneficiary for their countries of responsibility according to the distribution table (see Annex).

Prioritization was a learning experience for all partners involved. At the time of individual sessions, no prior knowledge was available about the potential reception of the Facility.

As a first step, partners need to establish the need or not to prioritise projects or beneficiaries according to:

- No of projects per beneficiary
- Mix of projects per beneficiary (new, ongoing, ending, closed)
- Whether to focus on a project level or beneficiary

As a second step, possible ways of reaching out were examined, in terms of:

- Organize small scale outreach events to attract interested beneficiaries
- Invite to individual sessions beneficiaries that were acquainted to the Facility's partners
- Invite the grant/innovation support offices within beneficiary institutions

As regards to the first step, smaller countries, such as Georgia and Armenia, did not need to prioritise due to the limited number of beneficiaries.

In cases of large volume of beneficiaries, initially the partners focused on the beneficiaries with many projects. However, it was later concluded that in case with large organisations with many projects, it was more difficult to attract their interest and convince them to submit an application in a more coordinated way.

Unfortunately, not all partners managed to recruit widening beneficiaries for individual sessions, due to resistance received by the beneficiaries contacted.

5. Beneficiaries and projects of individual sessions

Individual sessions were conducted with a small subset of the huge number of organisations implementing Widening actions primarily as coordinators and located in eligible countries of the Widening programme.

The outcome was 38 unique organisations representing 102 projects (95 unique) because in few cases several organisations that received information about the Facility participated in the same project. Furthermore, the projects were at diverse timing of their duration. Therefore, they were empirically categorized, apart from “Closed” and “New”, as “Ending” (when they have less than 6 months duration), as “Running” when they hadn’t reached their half duration and as “Mature” when they had up to 18 remaining months. The benchmark for this categorization was the date of the 1st cut-off, namely the 31st of July 2025.

Few details about the projects brought by recipients of individual sessions:

The number of projects per country that were introduced to the widerAdvance Facility were mainly related to the country of origin of the project partners.

The most common projects from beneficiaries interviewed came from the Twinning schemes.

Except the new projects which represent 1/3 of the projects brought in by the beneficiaries of Widening actions, the rest of the projects were theoretically capable of having produced key exploitable results that could be submitted to the widerAdvance Facility.

6. Unique organisations introduced to the WiderAdvance Facility

Widening beneficiary (organisation)	Country
YEREVAN STATE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY AFTER MKHITAR HERATSI	Armenia
INSTITUTE FOR PHYSICAL RESEARCH OF NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF ARMENIA	Armenia
STATE EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENT OF HIGHER PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION RUSSIAN-ARMENIAN (SLAVONIC) UNIVERSITY	Armenia
AMERICAN UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA FOUNDATION	Armenia
L.A .ORBELI INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOLOGY OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA STATE NON COMMERCIAL ORGANIZATION	Armenia
NATIONAL POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA FOUNDATION	Armenia
SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH INSTITUTE OF ENERGY	Armenia
Transilvania University of Braşov	Bulgaria

Medical University of Varna	Bulgaria
VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	Bulgaria
University of Zagreb	Croatia
University of Split, Faculty of Medicine (SVEUCILISTE U SPLITU MEDICINSKI FAKULTET)	Croatia
Talltech (TALLINNA TEHNIKAÜLIKOO)	Estonia
Environmental Investment Center (SIHTASUTUS KESKKONNAINVESTEERINGUTEKESKUS)	Estonia
University of Tartu (TARTU ULIKOOL)	Estonia
ILIA STATE UNIVERSITY	Georgia
GIORGI ELIAVA INSTITUTE OF BACTERIOPHAGY, MICROBIOLOGY AND VIROLOGY	Georgia
GEORGIAN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY	Georgia
University of Athens	Greece
Agricultural University of Athens	Greece
University of Crete	Greece
Patras University	Greece
P-NET ANADYOMENA DIKYTA NEAS GENIAS & EFARMOGES IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA (Competence center based in the city of Patras): PARTICIPANT	Greece
FORTH	Greece
HUN-REN SZAMITASTECHNIKAI ES AUTOMATIZALASI KUTATOINTEZET (HUN-REN Institute for Computer Science and Control)	Hungary
MISKOLCI EGYETEM (University of Miskolc)	Hungary
UNIVERSITE DE LA REUNION	La Reunion
CYROI	La Reunion
UNIVERSITA TA MALTA	Malta
NATIONAL CONTACT POINT AT GOVERNMENT OF MONTENEGRO	Montenegro
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY PARK MONTENEGRO (NAUCNO - TEHNOLOSKI PARK CRNE GORE)	Montenegro
INSTYTUT CHEMII FIZYCZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	Poland
UNIwersytet Warszawski	Poland
POLITECHNIKA LODZKA	Poland
UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	Portugal
Technical University of Bucharest (UNIVERSITATEA TEHNICA DE CONSTRUCTII BUCURESTI)	Romania
CENTRE DE RECHERCHE EN MICROELECTRONIQUE ET NANOTECHNOLOGIE AU TECHNOPOLE DE SOUSSE	Tunisia

7. APPENDIX –

7.1. List of organisations and projects

GREECE	ANDROMEDA	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Fostering balanced brain circulation - ERA Fellowships	1/9/2024	31/8/2026	13	MATURE
GREECE	TransEET	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	7	ENDING
GREECE	FunShield 4Med	University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/12/2022	30/11/2025	6	ENDING
GREECE	TALLHED A	Agricultural University of Athens (GEOPONIKO PANEPISTIMION ATHINON)	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	1/1/2024	30/6/2027	23	RUNNING
GREECE	REENFORCE	Agricultural University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Talents	1/9/2025	31/8/2029	36	NEW
GREECE	EU-CONEXUS ENABLES	Agricultural University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	1/2/2024	31/1/2029	42	NEW
GREECE	InPlasTwin	Agricultural University of Athens	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	26	NEW
GREECE	RACE	University of Crete (PANEPISTIMIO KRITIS)	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/3/2025	28/2/2030	55	NEW
GREECE	TALOS-AI4SSH	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/5/2024	30/4/2027	21	RUNNING
GREECE	TRIAD	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	1/5/2024	30/4/2027	21	RUNNING
GREECE	TWIN4Ear LiStAge	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	NEW
GREECE	ESPERANCE	Patras University (PANEPISTIMIO PATRON)	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/2/2023	31/1/2028	20	MATURE

GREECE	METACITES	Patras University	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
GREECE	MILESTONE	Patras University	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	21	MATURE
GREECE	UMA3	Patras University	HORIZON 2020	Twinning	1/9/2020	31/8/2023		CLOSED
GREECE	PharmGenHUB	Patras University	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Western Balkans Special	1/7/2022	30/6/2025		CLOSED
GREECE	CHAngeing	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/9/2024	31/8/2024		CLOSED
GREECE	DxHub	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2025	31/7/2027	24	NEW
GREECE	Edu4Climate	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Capacity building to strengthen networks of higher education institutions and cooperation with surrounding ecosystems	1/10/2022	30/9/2026	14	MATURE
GREECE	WIDEnzymes	University of Crete	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	1/1/2024	31/3/2027	18	MATURE
GREECE	METACITES	P-NET ANADYOMENA DIKTYA NEAS GENIAS & EFARMOGES IDIOTIKI KEFALAIOUCHIKI ETAIREIA (Competence center based in the city of Patras): PARTICIPANT	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
GREECE	DemosAxia	FORTH (IDRYMA TECHNOLOGIAS KAI EREVNAS)	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (downstream)	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	RUNNING
GREECE	BRIDGE	FORTH	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING

GREECE	DYNASTY	FORTH	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/11/2022	31/10/2025	3	ENDING
POLAND	CREATE	INSTYTUT CHEMII FIZYCZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	H2020	ERA Chairs	1/10/2015	31/3/2021		CLOSED
POLAND	PERFECTION	INSTYTUT CHEMII FIZYCZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/3/2025	28/2/2030	55	NEW
POLAND	TRIO-VI CoE	INSTYTUT CHEMII FIZYCZNEJ POLSKIEJ AKADEMII NAUK	HORIZON EUROPE	Teaming for Excellence	1/1/2025	31/12/2030	65	NEW
POLAND	MitoPNP	UNIwersYTET WARSZAWSKI	H2020	Widening Fellowships	1/9/2021	31/8/2023		CLOSED
POLAND	ENGHUM	UNIwersYTET WARSZAWSKI	H2020	Twinning	1/1/2016	31/12/2018		CLOSED
POLAND	TRAINCREASE	UNIwersYTET WARSZAWSKI	H2020	Twinning	1/1/2021	30/6/2024		CLOSED
POLAND	CONDEM	UNIwersYTET WARSZAWSKI	HORIZON EUROPE	Fostering balanced brain circulation - ERA Fellowships	1/5/2024	31/10/2026	15	MATURE
POLAND	PATHFOOD	UNIwersYTET WARSZAWSKI	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	NEW
POLAND	SYNCC-IN	UNIwersYTET WARSZAWSKI	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	25	NEW
POLAND	AldesignTEX	POLITECHNIKA LODZKA	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	25	NEW
POLAND	SustDesignTex	POLITECHNIKA LODZKA	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
CROATIA	AIFORS	University of Zagreb (SVEUCILISTE U ZAGREBU FAKULTET ELEKTROTEHNIKE I RACUNARSTVA)	H2020	ERA Chairs	1/1/2021	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
CROATIA	EXCELLABUST	University of Zagreb	H2020	Twinning	1/1/2016	31/12/2018		CLOSED
CROATIA	AeRoTwin	University of Zagreb	H2020	Twinning	1/9/2018	28/2/2022		CLOSED
CROATIA	MARBLE	University of Zagreb	HORIZON EUROPE	Teaming for Excellence	1/1/2025	31/12/2030	65	NEW

CROATIA	UWIN-LABUST	University of Zagreb	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/1/2023	31/12/2027	29	MATURE
CROATIA	AeroSTRE AM	University of Zagreb	HORIZON EUROPE	Capacity building to strengthen networks of higher education institutions and cooperation with surrounding ecosystems	1/7/2022	30/6/2025		CLOSED
CROATIA	AloTwin	University of Zagreb	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
CROATIA	InnoThyroGen	University of Split, Faculty of Medicine (SVEUCILISTE U SPLITU MEDICINSKI FAKULTET)	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2025	31/12/2028	41	NEW
ROMANIA	EU-CONEXUS ENABLES	Technical University of Bucharest (UNIVERSITATEA TEHNICA DE CONSTRUCTII BUCURESTI)	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	1/2/2024	31/1/2029	42	NEW
ROMANIA	eHERITAGE	Transilvania University of Braşov (UNIVERSITATEA TRANSILVANIA DIN BRASOV)	H2020	Twinning	1/11/2015	31/10/2018		CLOSED
ROMANIA	AI4AGRI	Transilvania University of Braşov	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
BULGARIA	TRANSTEM	Medical University of Varna	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/10/2019	31/7/2025		CLOSED
CZECHIA	GeoUS	VSU - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	H2020	Twinning	1/1/2020	30/6/2023		CLOSED
CZECHIA	CESAR	VSU - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/2/2025	31/1/2030	54	NEW
CZECHIA	EBEAM	VSU - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/1/2024	31/12/2028	39	RUNNING
CZECHIA	MERGE	VSU - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	RUNNING

CZECHIA	CLARA	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	Teaming for Excellence	1/11/2024	31/10/2030	63	NEW
CZECHIA	TWIN SYNERGIES	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	1/5/2024	30/4/2026	9	MATURE
CZECHIA	SAN4Fuel	VSB - TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY OF OSTRAVA	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/11/2022	31/10/2025		CLOSED
TUNISIA	PRIMiNaS	CENTRE DE RECHERCHE EN MICROELECTRONIQUE ET NANOTECHNOLOGIE AU TECHNOPOLE DE SOUSSE	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
ARMENIA	COBRAIN	YEREVAN STATE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY AFTER MKHITAR HERATSI	H2020	Twinning	1/10/2019	31/5/2023		CLOSED
ARMENIA	MaNaCa	INSTITUTE FOR PHYSICAL RESEARCH OF NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF ARMENIA	H2020	Twinning	1/10/2019	31/3/2023		CLOSED
ARMENIA	ARICE	YEREVAN STATE MEDICAL UNIVERSITY AFTER MKHITAR HERATSI	H2020	Twinning	1/9/2020	31/12/2023		CLOSED
ARMENIA	NanoQIQO	STATE EDUCATIONAL ESTABLISHMENT OF HIGHER PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION RUSSIAN-ARMENIAN (SLAVONIC) UNIVERSITY	H2020	Twinning	1/1/2021	30/6/2024		CLOSED
ARMENIA	ETICA	AMERICAN UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA FOUNDATION	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/3/2025	28/2/2030	55	NEW
ARMENIA	NAR-SAR-IPH	L.A .ORBELI INSTITUTE OF PHYSIOLOGY OF THE NATIONAL ACADEMY OF SCIENCES OF THE REPUBLIC OF ARMENIA STATE NON COMMERCIAL ORGANIZATION	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/12/2022	30/11/2027	25	MATURE

ARMENIA	STREACS	AMERICAN UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA FOUNDATION	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	RUNNING
ARMENIA	STREACS	NATIONAL POLYTECHNIC UNIVERSITY OF ARMENIA FOUNDATION	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	RUNNING
ARMENIA	STREACS	SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH INSTITUTE OF ENERGY	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	1/6/2024	31/5/2027	22	RUNNING
GEORGIA	CHARM-Vis	ILIA STATE UNIVERSITY	H2020	Widening Fellowships	1/7/2019	30/6/2021		CLOSED
GEORGIA	ASCLEPIUS	GIORGI ELIAVA INSTITUTE OF BACTERIOPHAGY , MICROBIOLOGY AND VIROLOGY	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	23	RUNNING
GEORGIA	GAIN	GEORGIAN TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
MALTA	ERA_SHUTTLE	UNIVERSITA TA MALTA	HORIZON EUROPE	Fostering balanced brain circulation - ERA Talents	1/9/2023	31/8/2027	24	RUNNING
MALTA	EXCEL4MED	UNIVERSITA TA MALTA	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
MONTENEGRO	MONTEVITIS	NATIONAL CONTACT POINT AT GOVERNMENT OF MONTENEGRO	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Western Balkans Special	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
MONTENEGRO	MONUSEN	NATIONAL CONTACT POINT AT GOVERNMENT OF MONTENEGRO	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Western Balkans Special	1/6/2022	31/5/2025		CLOSED
MONTENEGRO	BCThubs	NATIONAL CONTACT POINT AT GOVERNMENT OF MONTENEGRO	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
MONTENEGRO	CROSS-REIS	NATIONAL CONTACT POINT AT GOVERNMENT OF MONTENEGRO	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	1/1/2024	31/12/2028	41	NEW

MONTENEGRO	POLICY ANSWERS	SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY PARK MONTENEGRO (NAUCNO - TEHNOLOSKI PARK CRNE GORE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Support for R&I policy making in the Western Balkans	1/3/2022	28/2/2026	7	MATURE
PORTUGAL	CHAngeing	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2023	31/12/2026	17	MATURE
PORTUGAL	MIA-Portugal	UNIVERSIDADE DE COIMBRA	HORIZON 2020	Teaming Phase 2	1/1/2020	31/12/2027	29	MATURE
LA REUNION	REALISTIC	UNIVERSITE DE LA REUNION	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Chairs	1/12/2022	30/11/2027	28	MATURE
LA REUNION	TwinSolar	UNIVERSITE DE LA REUNION	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/9/2022	30/11/2025	4	ENDING
LA REUNION	FOCUS-4R	CYROI	HORIZON EUROPE	ERA Talents	1/9/2025	31/8/2029	47	NEW
ESTONIA	BALTIC-FIT	Talltech (TALLINNA TEHNIKAÜLIKOOL)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	RUNNING
ESTONIA	MarTe	Environmental Investment Center (SIHTASUTUS KESKKONNAINV ESTEERINGUTEK ESKUS)	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2025	31/12/2028	41	NEW
ESTONIA	OH-BOOST	University of Tartu (TARTU ULIKOOL)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
UKRAINE	BIONAN OSENS	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	H2020	Twinning	1/10/2020	31/5/2024		CLOSED
UKRAINE	NEUROTWIN	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	H2020	Twinning	1/8/2019	31/7/2022		CLOSED
UKRAINE	BRIDGE	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	1/9/2024	31/8/2027	25	NEW

UKRAINE	AGRI-BIOCIRCULAR-HUB	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2025	31/12/2028	42	NEW
UKRAINE	HELIOS	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Green Deal	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	26	NEW
UKRAINE	ECOTWIN S	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
UKRAINE	SURE-AMR	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning Bottom-Up	1/10/2024	30/9/2027	26	NEW
UKRAINE	TWISMA	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/1/2023	31/12/2025	5	ENDING
UKRAINE	ECOTWIN S	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Twinning	1/10/2022	30/9/2025	2	ENDING
UKRAINE	EDUC-WIDE	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	European Excellence Initiative	1/3/2024	28/2/2027	19	RUNNING
UKRAINE	APPROACH (multiple participation)	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Fostering balanced brain circulation - ERA Talents	1/6/2023	30/11/2026	16	MATURE
UKRAINE	WaterWise Hub (mentoring under mentoring scheme)	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Excellence Hubs	1/1/2025	31/12/2028	43	NEW

UKRAINE	WIDE AcrossEU	Horizon Europe office in Ukraine (NATIONAL RESEARCH FOUNDATION IN UKRAINE)	HORIZON EUROPE	Pathways to Synergies (upstream)	1/5/2024	31/8/2027	25	RUNNING
HUNGARY	EPIC- Centre of Excellence in Production Informatics and Control	HUN-REN SZAMITASTECHNIKAI ES AUTOMATIZALAS I KUTATOINTEZET (HUN-REN Institute for Computer Science and Control)	H2020	Teaming Phase 2	1/4/2017	30/9/2024	10	CLOSED
HUNGARY	UMA3	MISKOLCI EGYETEM (University of Miskolc)	H2020	Twinning	1/9/2020	31/8/2023	23	CLOSED

7.2. Distribution Table

No.	Partner	Type	Countries to be covered
1.	IPPT PAN (PL)	REC	Poland, Ukraine, Romania, Serbia, Croatia
2.	FORTH (EL)	NCP Hosting organisation	Greece, Cyprus, Bulgaria
3.	UNICO (CZ)	SME	Czechia
4.	CVTI SR (SK)	NCP Hosting organisation	Slovakia, Slovenia
5.	EM (HU)	SME	Hungary
6.	RCL (LT)	NCP Hosting organisation	Lithuania, Latvia, Estonia
7.	MHESR (TN)	NCP Hosting organisation	Tunisia, Morocco, Turkey
8.	SIPAC (AM)	NCP Hosting organisation	Armenia, Georgia
9.	MCST (MT)	NCP Hosting organisation	Malta, Montenegro, Kosovo, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Moldova, Faroe Islands, Albania
10.	RUIZIA (FR)	Regional agency	French Outermost Regions
11.	FCRT (PT)	Regional agency	Portuguese Outermost Regions + Portugal (continental part)
12.	ACIISI (ES)	Regional agency	Spanish Outermost Regions

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